

Modus Operandi protocol

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Table of Contents:

Modus Operandi protocol.....	2
Contributors.....	4
Revision history	4
1. Executive summary.....	6
2. Introduction: Definitions.....	7
2.1. Modus Operandi	7
2.2. Modus Operandi's building blocks	8
3. MO protocol: recommendations of guiding principles and practical features with KPIs.....	9
4. Conclusion and next steps	14
Highlights from the recommendations.....	14
Perspectives	15
Next Steps	15
5. Annex 1: Methodology: brief, technical presentation of methods used	16
5.1. Task process.....	16
5.2. Modus Operandi workshop on Ideal Partnership.....	16
5.3. Collecting practical insights	17
6. Annex 2: Results.....	21
6.1. Ideal partnership vision from brainstorming with experts.....	21
6.2. Practical insights from the PTF4LS case study.....	31
6.3. Practical insights from three INRAE in-depth case studies.....	34
6.4. Good practices in projects managed by INRAE Transfert.....	35
7. Annex 3: Full list of ideas from individual post-its during phase 1 of the workshop "Dreamt Future 37	
8. Annex 4: Facilitator guide for the Modus Operandi workshop on Ideal Partnership	39

1. Executive summary

This document outlines recommendations for the implementation and management of partnerships related to food systems, specifically focusing on the new Modus Operandi (MO) for a European Partnership Sustainable Food Systems. Derived from comprehensive collaborative efforts and field studies (see methodology and results in annex), the recommendations aim to ensure the functionality and enhance the effectiveness of such partnerships.

The core of our recommendations centers around the integration of clear guiding principles and practical features, completed by Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for evaluating success. Key highlights include:

- **Project Coordination and Management:** Emphasis on proactive and adaptable coordination between, the coordinator, the project managing team, and consortium partners, crucial for steering the partnership effectively. Regular updates and transparent communication are recommended to constantly align ongoing activities with strategic goals.
- **Internal Communication:** Dynamic and inclusive communication channels are recommended to ensure all partners are consistently informed and engaged. Tools like digital platforms for real-time updates and regular consortium meetings will foster an environment of transparency and collaboration.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Introduction of comprehensive monitoring frameworks to assess the progress against the partnership's objectives. This involves regular interactions with governing bodies and the integration of an advisory board comprising external experts to provide impartial insights.
- **Risk Management and Compliance:** Development of a structured risk management plan and strict adherence to compliance standards are suggested to preemptively address potential challenges and ensure integrity throughout the partnership's implementation.
- **Financial Management:** Recommendations for rigorous financial oversight mechanisms to ensure accountability and optimal use of funds. This includes regular reviews and adaptations to prevent financial incoherence and ensure sustainability.
- **External Communication, Dissemination, and Consultation:** A proactive approach to external communication and engagement is advised, targeting visibility and impact of the partnership's outcomes. The establishment of a detailed outreach plan and use of modern communication tools will facilitate broader dissemination and stakeholder consultation.

These recommendations are designed to fortify the foundation of the partnership, ensuring robust, efficient, and transparent operations. The implementation of these guidelines is expected to significantly contribute to the partnership's success. In the context of the EU-driven and co-funded Partnership Sustainable Food Systems, implementation of these guidelines is further expected to significantly contribute to the alignment with the overarching objectives of Horizon Europe.

In this document, the word 'partnership' means a collaboration through a specific agreement between organizations/people to work together. This word is sometimes starting with a capital 'Partnership' to mean EU Partnerships as funded by the European Commission (EU). Several of the guiding principles, practical features and recommendations formulated can be applicable to partnerships in general and if targeted to the European Partnership Sustainable Food Systems, FutureFoodS is specifically mentioned.

2. Introduction: Definitions

2.1. Modus Operandi

'Modus Operandi' as described in the FOODPaths Grant Agreement: "Partnership's means of executing tasks and interacting with other Partnerships or initiatives. A New Modus Operandi builds on new working relationships between all different actors and the wider society; it converges to an inclusive governance model for the Prototype Partnership SFS, via a co-creating process and collective intelligence approach; the Modus Operandi serves as a steering wheel."

From Latin, *modus* means "manner, method" and *operandi* means "of working" i.e. a particular way of doing something (cf. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/modus-operandi>) or a distinct pattern or method of operation (cf. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/modus%20operandi>).

In the figure below, the word 'modus operandi' is not yet included, however, is strongly connected to the systemic approach represented in the body center of the bird. 'Modus operandi' could be represented as the central mechanism activating the wings and allowing it to change course when necessary. It can also be represented as the backbone of the bird as it provides stability.

Figure 1. The key elements of the prototype Partnership, presented as a bird (from MS05). Adapted from (hal-02934667); design INRAE, H. de Vries.

After a brainstorm with the partners involved in WP2, the following definition was agreed:

The Modus Operandi (MO) is one of the components of the partnership, and the way in which all other components (e.g. governance, observatory) are orchestrated using guiding principles (e.g. co-creation, systemic approach) and practical features (e.g. secretariat, internal communication processes and tools). As such, it is the basis for the overall functioning of the Partnership.

2.2. Modus Operandi's building blocks

Components: *the fundamental, structural parts that make up the Partnership.* These components include various aspects of the organization, such as governance structures, observatory, and other elements that are essential for its operation.

Guiding principles: *the foundational beliefs or values that shape the Partnership's organization and actions (e.g. decision-making, strategies, and interactions within the Partnership).* They are essential in directing how the Partnership operates on both strategic and operational levels, ensuring alignment with its overarching goals.

Practical features: *the tangible, operational elements that support the daily functioning and implementation of the Partnership's objectives.* These features are critical as they translate the components and guiding principles into actionable processes and tools that facilitate the smooth operations of the Partnership.

In Task 2.3, the three building blocks were approached differently:

- *Components* are broader than the MO itself as it relates to the Partnership as a whole. While the aim of the MO is to make all components work smoothly together, they are not part of the MO *per se*. As such, **components fall beyond the scope of this task and were not specifically addressed in MO recommendations**, although they were used throughout the task to define how the MO can support the Partnership and its components.
- On the other hand, *guiding principles* and *practical features* are an integral part of the MO. Thus in this report, **recommendations are formulated on guiding principles and practical features**.

3. MO protocol: recommendations of guiding principles and practical features with KPIs

The MO protocol is synthesized in the table below including for each MO activities: practical features, processes and tools to put in place, as well as recommendations for implementation and KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) to measure their efficiency. Several guiding principles are associated to several MO activities but the major ones to consider are indicated in the table 1 below. This protocol is based on the results gathered thanks to the task 2.3 methodology and results (see sections 5 and 6).

MO activities	Guiding principles	Practical Features	More explanations and recommendations	KPIs
Project coordination and management	Proactivity, adaptability, vision, trust	<p>Regular communication between the coordinator and the project manager to ensure alignment and address issues promptly.</p> <p>Clear roles and tasks distribution between the coordinator and the project manager, as well as partners.</p> <p>Clear and accessible management tools and procedures for the coordination team and the consortium.</p>	<p>The coordination team composed of at least the coordinator and the project manager (also called 'secretariat' in certain cases) are the partnerships pilots. They shall be involved since the beginning of the partnership and have enough resources to perform the activities. The human qualities and relationship between both are crucial to lead the partnership. They shall activate the governing bodies when needed (e.g. decision-making, partnership monitoring).</p> <p>Digital tools are opportunities to meet regularly (if not on the same site), and to share and monitor the progress of the different coordination/ management actions (e.g. Trello, task Planner).</p>	<p>Coordination meetings at least every two weeks.</p> <p>Schedule of coordination/management actions updated at least every two weeks.</p>
Internal communication	Transparency, trust, collaboration, cohesion, inclusivity, consensus building	<p>Efficient internal communication tools adapted to partners' needs.</p> <p>Regular communications to inform about the partnership progress, including results obtained and visibility of</p>	<p>The internal communication, driven by the coordination team, is crucial to create a good atmosphere and favor interactions and collaboration among partners. It shall allow partners to better know each other, to have an overview of the partnership progress, and to realize the work plan.</p>	<p>Online collaborative / sharing platform setup at the partnership start and updated every month.</p> <p>Update the handbook setup at the partnership start and updated every two years</p>

MO activities	Guiding principles	Practical Features	More explanations and recommendations	KPIs
		<p>various activities implemented by partners, both internal and external.</p> <p>Innovative activities and tools to favor partner's interactions and collective intelligence.</p> <p>Regular consortium meetings each with a specific aim, modality (in-person or virtual), and frequency.</p>	<p>Efficient communication tools include online collaborative / sharing platform allowing each partner to gain insights from and build on experiences from all (e.g. written Q&A or FAQ, forum type exchanges, recorded webinars, etc.).</p> <p>For partners who are not used to be part of partnerships, formal tools such as handbook clarifying how the partnership is functioning, common goals and mutual interests can be setup to give a strong sense of belonging where each partner find its place and foster collaboration within the partnership.</p> <p>During the events, it is important to setup a frame but also leave time for informal/free interactions. Innovative activities (e.g. world café, fish bowl, icebreakers) and tools (e.g. white boards such as Klaxoon tool) are opportunities to favor collective intelligence, free expression of each and cohesion. The coordination team can support partners to organize such innovative activities.</p>	<p>when the Grant Agreement is amended.</p> <p>Internal bulletin to inform about the partnership progress sent by e-mail every three months.</p> <p>Partnership general physical meeting every year gathering all partners.</p> <p>Informal short virtual meetings gathering all partners every month for free exchanges (plus organize one-by-one exchanges if needed).</p>
Monitoring and evaluation	Continuous assessment, adaptability	<p>Management tools and procedures to monitor the partnership progress and perform the reporting to the funding agency.</p> <p>Regular communication between the coordination team and the governing bodies/ partners in charge of the partnership monitoring.</p> <p>Advisory board composed of external experts.</p>	<p>The coordination team shall propose such tools and procedures but it must be agreed with the other partners in charge of the partnership monitoring (e.g. work package leaders) to favor their adoption. These partners shall support the coordination team to ensure a global monitoring. Digital tools are opportunities to meet regularly, and to monitor the partnership progress (i.e. follow milestones, deliverables, tasks progress) (e.g. files on shared tools such as SharePoint, NextCloud).</p> <p>The evaluation is mostly done by the funding agency (supported by external experts), but the</p>	<p>Monitoring meetings with the governing bodies/ partners in charge at least every four months.</p> <p>Monitoring files shared and updated at least every four months.</p> <p>Evaluation by the funding agency or an advisory board every year.</p>

MO activities	Guiding principles	Practical Features	More explanations and recommendations	KPIs
			partnership can also setup an advisory board composed of relevant external experts choose by the consortium to provide guidance and advices on the partnership progress, in light and link to other initiatives/ projects/ partnerships.	
Quality of management and communication measures	Continuous improvement, adherence to tools and procedures, consensus building	<p>Management tools and procedures centralized in a management guidelines.</p> <p>Review system to control the quality of results/ deliverables.</p> <p>Feedback mechanism to continuously improve the tools and procedures.</p>	<p>The coordination team shall propose such tools and procedures but it must be agreed with the other partnership partners, especially governing bodies, to favor their adoption.</p> <p>Regarding the partnerships results/ deliverables, it is important to involve and nominate other partners to review them, knowing that the work package leaders and coordination team shall have a final review on them.</p> <p>Feedback mechanism includes complementary levels e.g. combine informal feedback to gather direct impressions, with formal feedback methods such as anonymous questionnaires that allow everyone to share their views on an equal footing.</p>	<p>Feedback meetings in the coordination team and surveys with the consortium to evaluate the efficiency of management tools and procedure at least twice a year.</p> <p>Surveys with the consortium to evaluate the efficiency of internal communication tools and practices at least twice a year.</p> <p>Setup a management guidelines at the partnership start and updated it every year if needed based on partners' feedbacks.</p>
Risk management	Anticipation, proactivity, adaptability	Risk management plan for risk identification and efficient mitigation measures.	The coordination team shall propose such tool to be used with the partnership bodies / partners involved in the partnership monitoring in order to update it continuously (e.g. new risks, update the level of risk low/medium/high, the severity low/medium/high, and the mitigation measures).	Risk management plan updated at least every four months.
Compliance with legal rules	Compliance, integrity, flexibility, fairness	<p>European Commission rules compliance by the consortium.</p> <p>Transparent and flexible internal rules, including for</p>	The coordination team has the role to make the EC rules (part of the Grant Agreement) respected by the consortium. However, these rules are sometimes difficult to understand especially for partners how are not used to be	Remind of the EC rules during each partnership events and through internal bulletins at least once a year.

MO activities	Guiding principles	Practical Features	More explanations and recommendations	KPIs
		<p>new partner assessment process.</p>	<p>part in partnerships. So, the coordination team must remind them (e.g. during partnership events) and popularized them (e.g. in a management guidelines, in the internal bulletin) in order to be understandable by all partners.</p> <p>Internal rules (not part of the Grant Agreement) are usually written in a Consortium Agreement signed between all partners (e.g. partnership results dissemination, intellectual property, funding mechanism among partners). These rules are agreed among partners and can evolve/be flexible depending on the situation.</p>	<p>Grant Agreement amended every two years.</p> <p>Consortium Agreement amended every two years at the same time of the Grant Agreement.</p>
Financial management	Regular monitoring, viability	<p>Regular internal financial review for optimal financial management.</p> <p>Tools for financial reporting to the EC (link to the Monitoring and evaluation activity).</p> <p>Strategy for financial viability of the partnership.</p>	<p>The coordination team shall propose such tools and procedures. Digital tools are opportunities for a smooth financial review and prepare the reporting to the EC (e.g. files on shared tools such as SharePoint, NextCloud). Optimal financial management reduce the risk of financial deviation and allow allocation of resources in due time.</p> <p>Regarding the strategy for financial viability of the partnership, this is one of the most critical point of FutureFoodS which needs to be negotiated with partners and the EC.</p>	<p>Perform financial review per partner every year (officially via EC reporting, and if necessary via intermediate questionnaires).</p> <p>Negotiate (with the EC and partners) the strategy of the Partnership funding every two years when the Grant Agreement is amended.</p>
External communication, dissemination and consultation	Collaboration, inclusivity, transparency, openness, sustainability, impact	<p>Outreach plan with clear objectives, roadmap and quantitative KPIs to assess and revise the plan.</p> <p>Efficient external communication tools adapted to target audiences to communicate, disseminate and consult them.</p>	<p>External communication and dissemination of the partnership activities and findings has the main goal to ensure its global outreach. It encompasses the proactive expansion of the partnership network including diverse stakeholders, citizens and international organizations. The outreach plan shall be co-created with partners in order to favor their engagement.</p>	<p>Setup the outreach plan at the partnership start with the support of partners and update it every year or 18 months.</p> <p>Setup the public website at the partnership start and update it when needed, at least every two months.</p>

MO activities	Guiding principles	Practical Features	More explanations and recommendations	KPIs
		<p>Mapping of the existing initiatives, projects, partnerships to link with, and setup a database of key actors.</p> <p>Feedback rounds to re-discuss the plan (including its objectives) and improve the strategy.</p>	<p>Classical tools such as partnership website to showcase outcomes both in English and national language is a safe bet.</p> <p>This plan shall contribute to enhance strategic alignment and avoid duplications (e.g. in the writing of open calls) through cross-partnership discussions (e.g. in ‘small environment’) and shared knowledge practices (e.g. setup a community of practices).</p> <p>As an ultimate goal, the plan shall ensure the partnership results exploitation and long-term impact.</p> <p>Regarding consultation, it is important to get balanced contribution of stakeholders and use a mix of tools to solicit them, especially when updating the SRIA.</p> <p>It is important that the plan clearly identifies quantitative KPIs and the means to measure them, as well as regular timeframes in which assess results obtained. This will open a transparent and open discussion with relevant stakeholders to update and improve the strategy, including the potential re-definition of strategy’s objectives.</p>	<p>Perform a mapping of the existing at the partnership start with a database of key actors and update it when needed, at least every six months.</p> <p>Setup quantitative KPIs to monitor each activity (i.e., number of participants to events, number of downloads from the website, etc.) and their regular update (at least, every year).</p>

4. Conclusion and next steps

This deliverable D2.5 presents a framework for the Modus Operandi (MO) of European Partnerships, with a particular focus on fostering sustainable food systems through inclusive and innovative collaboration. Developed through a co-creative process involving extensive stakeholder input, practical case studies, and shared experience, the recommendations offer actionable insights into guiding principles, practical features, and measurable KPIs to support effective partnership functioning.

Highlights from the recommendations

The recommendations outlined in Section 3 of this deliverable emphasize the critical elements necessary for efficient and adaptive partnership management. These include:

- **Effective coordination and management:** establishing clear roles, robust internal communication, and regular coordination exchanges to ensure alignment among diverse stakeholders.
- **Dynamic internal and external communication:** promoting trust and inclusivity through transparent communication processes, innovative tools, and consistent updates to partners and the public.
- **Monitoring, evaluation, and continuous improvement:** implementing KPIs to measure the effectiveness of partnership activities and foster continuous adaptation to evolving challenges.
- **Risk and financial management:** enhancing resilience through structured risk identification, mitigation strategies, and rigorous financial oversight mechanisms.
- **External outreach and stakeholder engagement:** developing targeted dissemination strategies to expand the partnership's influence and ensure the integration of diverse perspectives.

In the context of food systems, these recommendations aim to bridge the gap between research, policy, and practice. By fostering collaboration across sectors, enhancing knowledge sharing, and supporting innovative practices, the Modus Operandi outlined here contributes to the systemic transformation needed to achieve sustainable food systems¹. These guiding principles and practical features ensure that the partnership's activities remain aligned with long-term goals while delivering measurable impacts.

Consideration for tailoring the Modus Operandi. While the proposed Modus Operandi provides a robust framework, feedback has highlighted the need for further tailoring to address the unique characteristics of the FutureFoodS Partnership². As a co-funded, public-public partnership encompassing 86 partners, FutureFoodS requires specific adaptations to account for its scale and structure. These considerations will be addressed in future iterations of the governance framework, including the Manual & Presentation of the Prototype 2.0 Partnership SSFS (Deliverable D2.7), which extends beyond the Modus Operandi to cover the broader governance model.

¹ European Commission. (2024). European Partnerships for Sustainable Food Systems. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/partnerships_en

² FutureFoodS Partnership. (2024). FutureFoodS: A Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems. Retrieved from <https://www.futurefoodpartnership.eu>

Perspectives

Looking ahead, several perspectives deserve exploration to refine the Modus Operandi further and enhance its applicability to diverse partnerships:

1. **Cultural dimensions in management:** building on Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory³ ⁴, the interplay between culture and management styles within partnerships should be examined. Understanding how cultural differences influence decision-making, communication, and collaboration can provide valuable insights for tailoring the Modus Operandi to varied organizational and regional contexts.
2. **Integration of digital tools and innovations:** the role of digital platforms and tools in facilitating efficient partnership operations, knowledge sharing, and stakeholder engagement should be further explored. Emerging technologies such as AI-driven analytics and virtual collaboration tools could significantly enhance the operational efficiency and inclusivity of partnerships⁵ ⁶.
3. **Scaling and adaptability:** strategies for scaling partnership practices to accommodate growth while maintaining functionality and coherence should be developed. This is particularly relevant for FutureFoodS, where expanding the network to include new stakeholders and regions will require a flexible yet structured approach.
4. **Cross-partnership collaboration:** strengthening synergies with other partnerships and initiatives working on related goals⁷ can amplify impact and prevent duplication of efforts. Developing communities of practice and shared resources can foster strategic alignment and mutual learning.

Next Steps

The findings and recommendations of this deliverable will inform the ongoing development of governance models for European Partnerships. A roadmap based on the proposed KPIs will guide the implementation and evaluation of the Modus Operandi, ensuring continuous improvement and alignment with strategic objectives. Collaboration with all stakeholders will remain central to these efforts, ensuring inclusivity and adaptability.

The insights presented here represent a crucial step toward achieving systemic transformation in food systems. By embedding co-creation, transparency, and adaptability into partnership operations, FutureFoodS and similar initiatives can drive impactful change and contribute to the realization of sustainable food systems across Europe and beyond.

³ Hofstede, G. (1980). *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-Related Values*. Sage Publications

⁴ Hofstede Insights. (2023). Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory. Retrieved from <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/models/national-culture/>

⁵ Gartner. (2024). "AI-Enabled Collaboration Platforms: Transforming Organizational Efficiency and Engagement". Gartner Research Report, Technology Innovation Series

⁶ McKinsey & Company. (2023). "The Future of Work: AI, Digital Collaboration, and Organizational Transformation". McKinsey Digital Insights Report

⁷ European Commission. Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment - European Partnerships under Horizon Europe. European Commission Research and Innovation. Retrieved November 29, 2024, from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe/food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment_en

5. Annex 1: Methodology: brief, technical presentation of methods used

5.1. Task process

The following process was defined in order to shape the prototype Partnership's Modus Operandi. In this deliverable D2.5, the steps 1 to 4 were considered.

Figure 2. Process defined to shape the prototype Partnership's MO.

5.2. Modus Operandi workshop on Ideal Partnership

Context: Applying the task process, the first two steps 'Dreamt future' and 'Situations' were performed through a collaborative session organized in December 2023 (as a side event of the FOOD2030 conference in Brussels) with FOODPathS partners, some Advisory Board members and other invited actors (e.g. from existing Partnerships, the EC).

Workshop description: The collaborative session was conducted in 3 phases (see facilitator's guide in annex 2):

- Phase 1 – Dreamt ideal Partnership:** brainstorming, sharing and pooling in plenary session in order to identify 'Success pillars', i.e. key successes and features of the ideal Partnership; take hereby into account the societal and environmental challenges we are facing.
- Phase 2 – Four example situations of the Partnership:** scriptwriting, testing and updating each situation in small groups about 6 persons each. Four complementary situations reflecting successive phases (but not covering the entire Partnership life cycle), each illustrating one working method of the Partnership through an example or practical situation of the Partnership's activities, were proposed for each table. Each situation is further described in the 'Results' section of this report.
- Phase 3 – Story-telling and assessment:** pitch the situations and vote for critical actions to keep, clarify or adapt (hence to assess as well as possible) in plenary session. It should be noted that most favorable (or 'prioritized') actions are defined by the participants in the discussion group, also taking into account each other's different contexts.

5.3. Collecting practical insights

5.3.1. The PTF4LS case study

Context: The Food4Life (F4L) workshop during EFFoST conference in November 2023 was organized in collaboration with WP4. It was the opportunity to gather input of good practices regarding the functioning of existing partnerships, with a focus on the *modus operandi* and the added value of public-private collaboration.

Presentation of actors of the PTF4LS network: The Platform Tecnológica Food for Life-Spain (PTF4LS), coordinated by FIAB, may be seen as one example of a partnership dedicated to advancing sustainable food systems, at national scale. As an extensive collaborative network, PTF4LS integrates numerous sector associations and regional clusters, collectively representing a significant portion of the Spanish agri-food sector. This broad range facilitates a comprehensive approach to addressing the challenges and needs inherent in sustainable innovation and industry development in Spain.

Mirroring the European Technology Platform Food for Life, PTF4LS aligns its strategic objectives with broader European initiatives, focusing on innovation and sustainability in the food sector. This strategic alignment ensures that the initiatives and goals of PTF4LS contribute meaningfully to both national and European agendas, enhancing their relevance and impact.

Through FIAB, PTF4LS functions with structured governance and effective collaboration, seen as essential for driving impactful research and development outcomes. The network engages a diverse group of stakeholders, which comprises 170 partner organizations including 97 companies, 33 research and technology centers, 16 universities, and 15 associations, reflecting a robust cross-section of the food industry from SMEs to large corporations and academic institutions.

PTF4LS also showcases its commitment to R&D through the mobilization of substantial resources, with the network facilitating the participation in projects funded by national and European grants. These projects not only advance technological innovations but also address critical sustainability challenges in food production and consumption.

In summary, PTF4LS serves as an exemplary case, at national level, for partnerships of diverse actors in sustainable food systems. The platform illustrates how structured collaboration and comprehensive stakeholder engagement can effectively address complex sustainability issues within the food systems, possibly providing a scalable model for other national and international initiatives.

Presentation of the six responding organizations: Six of the 170 PTF4LS partner organizations participated to the F4L workshop, representing the network's diverse organizational types. They are presented in Table 2.

Organization	Type	Description
FIAB (Spanish Food and Drink Industry Federation)	Association	FIAB represents the Spanish food and drink industry, comprising 45 sector associations and regional clusters. It serves as a collective voice for the industry, coordinating research and innovation efforts and linking with national and European policies.
CARTIF	Technological Center	CARTIF is a multi-disciplinary technological center that provides innovative solutions to the industry to enhance competitiveness. It participates in various research and development projects focusing on technological advances and sustainability in food systems.
UPV (Universitat Politècnica de Valencia)	University	UPV is a public research and education organization that specializes in science and technology. It contributes to the network by leading working groups focused on food service, driving research, education, and policy development in the food sector.

Organization	Type	Description
IATA-CSIC (Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology - Spanish National Research Council)	Governmental Research Institute	IATA-CSIC is part of the Spanish National Research Council, Spain's largest public research institution. It focuses on food science and technology, aligning its research activities with industry needs and participating actively in collaborative innovation projects.
CDTI (Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology)	Government Agency	CDTI is a public business entity, under the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, that promotes innovation and technological development in Spanish companies. It supports the network by facilitating access to funding for R&D projects and promoting international technological cooperation.
INGREDALIA	SME (Small and Medium-sized Enterprise)	INGREDALIA specializes in the development of upcycled ingredients from food waste, emphasizing sustainability and innovation in the agri-food industry. As a smaller enterprise, it brings agility and a specific focus on sustainable solutions to the network, highlighting the role of SMEs in driving niche innovations within broader research and industry platforms.

Questions addressed: The following questions were asked to the speakers prior to the workshop in order to consider them during their presentations:

1. What is the added value of being part of this private-public network (examples of successes)? What are your organization's goals in participating in the PTF4LS?
2. How do you collaborate with the different actors? What is the positive contribution of private actors to the goals of this network?
3. Does the network include all relevant stakeholders?
4. As a member of the PTF4LS, how does your organization integrate the administrative and financial rules of the network? (for example contact person, resources invested...)
5. How does PTF4LS ensure a sense of belonging within the network? In your opinion, what specific actions can be taken to enhance the sense of belonging?
6. Based your experience in private-public cooperation, what strategies can be used to effectively involve the food industry in a future EU partnership on sustainable food systems?

5.3.2. The three INRAE in-depth case studies

Context: An in-depth case study has been carried out within the WP2 during 2023 on four different partnerships. Data and results have been reported in the deliverable D2.3. If the content of interviews focused on governance, co-creation and sustainability topics, some elements related to the Modus Operandi on three of the four cases have been identified and discussed in this deliverable D2.5.

Selection of the three cases: After collecting 72 examples of food system cases (D2.1), which reveal all kinds of 'partnerships', with the support of the WP4 and WP7 partners, in-depth case studies were conducted on 3 'partnerships'. These reflect the diversity of scales and cover countries in the north, south, east, and west of Europe:

- Pôle Mer Méditerranée (regional, France);
- Foodwest (regional/national, Finland);
- BIOEAST (cross-countries, Central-Eastern countries of European Union).

Ten interviews per case were carried out in 2023 among diverse actors of each partnership regarding what could be learnt from their governance model, the actors involved, the value co-created, and the sustainability vision.

The three organizations which were selected for in-depth case studies are described in Table 3.

'Partnership' organization name	Description
Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM)	<p>PMM can be described as an innovation cluster covering two regions along the French Mediterranean coast. These regions are working together with their twin brother regions located in Britannia, on the Atlantic coast in France, united in the Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique. Both of them share the same objective: “building a carbon-free and sovereign blue economy, supporting sustainable growth and future jobs” (Pôle Mer Méditerranée, 2023). From this objective, the cluster derived 3 main ambitions: (i) enhancing innovation by structuring sectors, (ii) being a central point thanks to the connections and implementation of regional/national policies and (iii) promoting PMM’s members and their areas at the international level, while reinforcing its leadership within the Mediterranean basin.</p> <p>PMM counts more than 500 members divided into 4 different categories: big companies, SMEs, research & education centers, and the larger ecosystem (including banks, consulting agencies, NGOs, and so on).</p> <p>https://polemermediterranee.com/en/homepage/</p>
Foodwest (F)	<p>Foodwest is a medium-sized private company considered a major stakeholder in Finland today because its objective and creation context is unique. The services offered are quite broad, from the formulation of new recipes and packaging designs to studies on consumer behavior. They translate product ideas into concrete product concepts and then support their development, adding value to future products. It may not immediately be evident to consider Foodwest as a partnership, given its activities that are close to a consulting agency and its legal status as a private company. However, Foodwest is not a classical enterprise since it is more a shared service platform of national interest, driven by a partnership of universities, public institutions, and companies. Foodwest provides tools, solutions, and knowledge, and its owners/customers are providing the objectives, and are involved in a diverse set of activities.</p> <p>https://foodwest.fi/en/front-page/</p>
BIOEAST (BE)	<p>The first ambition of theBIOEAST Initiative is to voluntarily gather policymakers from 11 Central-Eastern European countries sharing the motivation to develop a circular, bioeconomy strategy in their countries. Their mission statement toward 2030 is the following: “to develop knowledge and cooperation based on circular bioeconomies, which helps to enhance their growth and to create new value-added jobs, especially in rural areas, maintaining or even strengthening environmental sustainability” (BIOEAST, 2024). The second ambition is to define bioeconomy clusters at different levels, from national to macro-regional scales, building a series of bioeconomy hubs. Each hub will serve as an established communication center on bioeconomy within BIOEAST countries.</p> <p>https://bioeast.eu/</p>

Interview process: Interviews for each case have begun with general question on the functioning of the partnership to better understand the global context. Some of the data collected were related to the Modus Operandi and are therefore relevant to report and analyze here.

5.3.3. Collecting good practices in projects managed by INRAE Transfert

Context: The European Department of INRAE Transfert (IT) was created in 2004 and has a long-term experience in managing a diversity of European projects (more than 100 projects). The IT staff is in a process of continuous improvement, capitalizing on each experience by organizing feedbacks with the coordinators with whom they work, and by evaluating the project’s management tools and procedures (deliverable D1.1) through surveys sent to the consortium. The project management being a practical feature of the MO, IT wanted to evaluate and share in this report its good practices and success factors leading to successful project management.

Workshop description: A collaborative workshop was organized in October 2024, involving 28 staff members (out of a total of 31) from the INRAE Transfert’s European Department, utilizing the Glowbl digital tool. The 'Appreciative Interviews' technique, derived from the [Liberating Structures](#) methodology,

was employed to facilitate exchanges among participants and to focus on positive and successful experiences. The workshop process was the following:

- 1) In groups of three, participants took turns recounting one or more successful experiences. The other participants paid attention to what made the success possible.
- 2) Then, in groups of six, each participant relayed the story of another. Then, together, they detected the conditions for success.
- 3) Finally, each group presented their work to all participants, opening up discussions and formalizing these keys to success.

6. Annex 2: Results

6.1. Ideal partnership vision from brainstorming with experts

Applying the task 2.3 process (see 'Methods'), the first two steps 'Dreamt future' and 'Situations' were addressed via a collaborative session organized in December 2023, as a side event of the FOOD2030 conference in Brussels. Participants were FOODPathS partners, Advisory Board members, and other invited actors (e.g., from existing Partnerships, the EC).

Phase 1 of the workshop focused on envisioning an ideal Partnership by brainstorming and identifying 'Success pillars', which capture the key successes and features of the ideal Partnership. In Phase 2, participants discussed four 'example situations' to illustrate representative activities of the ideal partnership.

6.1.1. Success pillars

Ideas from individual post-it's are listed in Annex 3.

We define a 'success pillar' as an area or activity of the Partnership that is critical for its overall effectiveness and achievement of its goals. This exercise brought out nine success pillars:

- 1. Ecosystem network:** Cultivates a robust environment around the partnership i.e. a network of stakeholders across the food chain, fostering trust and collaborative innovation, while promoting geographical diversity and multi-actor integration.
- 2. Dialogue & consensus building:** Serves as a neutral platform for building consensus among stakeholders and resolving divergent views, utilizing continuous improvement tools to enhance collaborative decision-making.
- 3. Scientific results & impact:** Drives impactful research and innovation, supporting high-quality projects that influence policy and societal behaviors towards sustainable food systems.
- 4. Science to policy:** Establishes a direct link between scientific research and policy-making, ensuring that insights and discoveries inform and guide food system transformations.
- 5. Co-creation with industry:** Joint execution of R&I projects and interactive dialogue on project results. Facilitates the adoption of research outputs by the food industry, leading to improved processes and sustainable practices.
- 6. Consultation & communication to citizens:** Engages EU citizens through effective communication strategies, ensuring widespread understanding and participation in the partnership's initiatives.
- 7. Training & education:** Integrates educational initiatives with outreach activities, enhancing public and academic involvement through practical applications and co-creation processes in e.g. living labs.
- 8. Global outreach:** Extends the partnership's impact globally through strategic dissemination and communication efforts, ensuring international engagement and collaboration.
- 9. Sustainable outcomes & shared vision:** Focuses on creating sustainable outcomes and cohesive strategy that aligns all partnership activities towards a unified vision of sustainable food systems (SFS).

Success pillars and tentative functional links between them are shown in the figure 2 below.

Figure 3. The nine key pillars of success for the ideal Partnership.

6.1.2. Setting the scene

To set the scene of the future Partnership four illustrations of the Partnership in action were addressed in this exercise. Their focus and description (as presented to workshop participants) are presented in Table 4.

Example Situation Focus (title)	Key Words	Description
1. Launch ("Seeing the Light")	Launch, unfamiliar partners, engagement, internal communication, community building	<p>"The Partnership is launched, not all partners are familiar with each other and some of them have never been involved in an EU Partnership. What are the measures to put in place among the different types of organizations involved in several activities, in order to promote internal communication, their engagement, and their understanding of what is expected from them?"</p> <p>Please consider: Tools, including digital; Event organization, including annual meeting ; Possible combination of project meetings with other activities and workshops running back-to-back.</p>

Example Situation Focus (title)	Key Words	Description
2. Engagement ("All Aboard")	Full participation, systems approach, SRIA update, stakeholder engagement both internal & external, flexibility in fund allocation, long-term trust building	<p>"The partnership for sustainable food systems has now reached full speed, and by all accounts it has become the ideal partnership everyone had dreamt of. One recognized particularities of this partnership is its unique work method as fully participatory including all relevant partners, actors, stakeholders, through co-creative processes and a systems approach."</p> <p>In this context, how to handle the process for updating the SRIA? Please consider also both external and internal R&I initiatives or projects, and how stakeholders inside and outside of the consortium could be involved.</p>
3. Expansion ("Enlarging the Family")	Expansion, integration of new partners and funders, amendment to Grant Agreement, attracting international stakeholders, considerations of conflict of interest	<p>"The Partnership is launched, and the consortium is already starting to draft the amendment to the Grant Agreement and associated annual work programmes. But how to attract new funders, new countries, and new stakeholders that could be not enough represented?"</p> <p>As this process is initiated, Poland, the UK, and Luxembourg express their wish to join the consortium as Cash-funders. But what is the process to integrate new partners and funders in the consortium? Consider the different steps, level of involvement of each actor, and validations required."</p>
4. Collaboration ("Weaving Connections")	Collaboration with other initiatives and Partnerships, establishing synergies through mapping and database creation, strategic discussions, and shared knowledge practices	"The Partnership cannot work in a bubble. On the contrary, it needs cooperation with other initiatives, projects, and partnerships. But how to materialize such synergies with other trajectories and initiatives? What will be concretely performed, why, and through which steps? (Feel free to choose 1-3 specific examples e.g. of already running or launching initiatives)."

Table 1. Presentation of the Partnership in action situations discussed in the MO Workshop.

6.1.2.1. How to favor engagement and good communication among Partnership actors

The main takeaways to favor engagement and good communication among Partnership actors are the importance to invest in **building trust and a community**, to give very **clear information** on how the Partnership works and how processes function, to make sure that all stakeholder groups can **find their place, have their voice** and can bring in their expertise, and to be **pro-active**. In Phase 3 of the workshop, it was underlined that the citizens and CSO are lacking in this situation.

Situation 1 with a focus on "Launch" was addressed by workshop participants as follows: first, the most important needs for the different actor groups were identified (in Table 5 below, similar needs appear in the same line) and then the potential measures to deal with them were proposed.

Project manager*	Research	Policy advisor	Private sector*	Philanthropic organization
Have a clear common roadmap, outcomes and also deliverables	Have clear common objectives for orientation	Specifying aims, goals of the Partnership		
Need for a framework and rules, and define the specific requirements		Set the framework for the program/project	Clear information how the Partnership functions/how are processes designed (e.g priority setting)	

Need for alignment of working practices to find common grounds which are compatible with the working practices of the single partners				
Favor a good atmosphere, create a 'safe space' within the consortium, to generate trust				Get trust in both ways
For a call/funded projects, put emphasis on connections and seek synergies				
			Need to clarify their role in the Partnership and possible ways to engage (this holds for the actors plus their possibly associated networks)	The ways to engage
			Know how to influence the partnership	Ensure that their voice is heard
			Understand the differences between other Partnerships	

The following possible measures were identified to deal with the needs identified above:

- Identification of areas or activities where different actors can bring in their expertise (commonly or more specifically (e.g. philanthropic actors and their potential to mobilize cities).
- Active engagement and ask all actors to give input.
- The Partnership should be pro-active and create entry points that are attractive for various target groups.
- The Partnership should be visible and present in the European research arena.
- Setup a 'target list' of "most wanted" organizations to reach out (e.g. for enlarging geographical coverage).
- Organize regular internal exchange among consortium partners, but information should be well transferred to external stakeholders as well.
- Some concrete ideas:
 - o Open info days (example CBE).
 - o In-person info day around call launch (e.g. SBEP).
 - o Internal informal meetings for exchange (e.g. FOODPathS Café meetings).
 - o Annual events offering special opportunities, both for consortium partners (internal) but also to funded projects partners (offering some free agenda spots that can be co-used).

6.1.2.2. How to favor the robust foundation and update of the SRIA

The main takeaways to favor the robust foundation and update of the SRIA are the importance to get **balanced contribution of stakeholders** and a **mix of tools** to solicit them, to **start from the existing documents/networks/knowledge**, to conduct **coordination meetings of Partnerships** to align in the writing

of open calls, allow some **flexibility** in the reallocation of funds, and get a **long term view with trust** between partners and on the SRIA foundation.

For the sake of reaching sustainable food systems, periodic reflective meeting about overall progress are needed with all actors involved.

In the example situation 2 focusing on “engagement”, three main actions were identified for updating the SRIA (in Table 6 below):

Important actions to consider	How to facilitate them
<p>Consultation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – An open consultation can really ensure that relevant opinions are collected? Or is there the risk that they are the expression of an individual perspective?; – CBE JU has an entity that represents already all the stakeholders of the sector, helping the definition/update of the SRIA; – SCAR facilitates the collection of the MS opinion/ideas and organized workshops with stakeholders; – JPI HDHL has consultative bodies they count on to collect inputs. 	<p>Important to get balanced contribution of stakeholders and to have a mix of tools, workshops, open consultations to get inputs for general to more specific topics.</p> <p>Need to start from existing documents, networks, knowledge and experiences</p>
<p>Synergies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Capitalize on existing SRIAs, networks, projects, results, living labs; – Coherence among all Partnerships; – Are synergies explored in an effective way? 	<p>Conduct coordination meetings of Partnerships from Cluster 6 and others (e.g. FutureFoodS, Water4All, Biodiversa, ERA4HEALTH).</p> <p>Need to work together in writing the open calls while seeking complementarities and avoiding overlaps.</p>
<p>Change:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Level of adaptability (to SFS, changes, new knowledge...); – Stick to long term goals. 	<p>Allow a “window of flexibility” (possibility to reallocate funds if something unexpected happen)</p> <p>Long term view with trust between partners and respecting the foundation of the SRIA agreed upon by a large actor group; this doesn't exclude an evolution of the SRIA due to new insights.</p> <p>Both to be ensured by the Partnership governance.</p>

6.1.2.3. How to enlarge the consortium

The main takeaways on how to enlarge the consortium are to **attract countries (also outside EU) not already involved**; consider **key actors** of each countries (e.g. involve ministries that want to be involved in the programming even if they get no budget); involve the **civil society** (beyond local government); the involvement of **private funders and any partner requires specific attention regarding conflicts of interest**. In any case, when adding new funders, this must be carefully evaluated within the project consortium, Partnership rules and the conditions of inclusion shall be ‘negotiated’ with the governance.

The situation of a cash funder wanting to join, which was addressed in the example situation 3 focusing on “expansion”, was not interpreted as an issue given that funders would be able to join ‘simply’ by making an amendment to the Grant Agreement during the period of ‘re-negotiation’ with the EC. However different funders that would potentially be more problematic were identified (in Table 7 below).

Funder profile	How to Address
Partners and funders outside the EU	This was seen as relevant due to the FS being international, and the inclusion of such partners could be very relevant to ensure working with partners on projects outside the EU if they have relation to the EU FS.

Parent agency with 0 budget	The discussion was based on a situation in Ireland, where the ministries give funding to the agencies belonging to them, and these agencies then join the Partnership. There is still a wish for the relevant ministry to also be included in the programming, and in the Partnership to ensure they have an overview of the processes, as well as a voice in the decision-making process.
Region (e.g., Belgium, Netherlands)	Since the regions would have funding to contribute (case of Belgium and Netherlands discussed), this does not appear as a huge issue. However, their funding rules may be different and need alignment with the ones in the Partnership.
Groupings or networked organizations (CBBI)	The discussion centered around the many different voices and agendas contained within a group like this. How such network organizations could be a way to incorporate the voices of civil society, by including citizens networks and groups? Some might struggle with funding and PMs.
Private funder	<p>The experience of some participants with other Partnerships and networks was discussed in which the idea to have private funders was ultimately abandoned. The main issue was seen as Undue Influence, and the potential for tarnishing of the Partnership in case a private funder is embroiled in a scandal.</p> <p>Potential steps where conflict of interest (Col) could emerge with the involvement of private funders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining the focus of the call; • Selection of projects; • Perception of bias by applicants: low application rate; • Interaction between EC, ministries & companies. Does this breach lobbying regulations? • IPR issues when working with private actors. Open access; • 'Image' of the Partnership; • If a company faces a scandal, reputation of the Partnership is impacted; • Public interest, health, transparency, citizen's trust. <p>The solutions proposed when adding a new funder are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All should accept open access rules & transparency; • Have a standardized contract; • Step in project with own money: decision is in the project consortium. A specific framework needed within the Partnership governance; • Transparent interface (like science to policy) but with limited access to results; • Making knowledge accessible & understandable for SMEs & local business clusters (e.g. Core Organic network)

Table 4.

6.1.2.4. How to favor the Partnership cooperation with other initiatives

The main takeaways to favor the Partnership cooperation with other initiatives are to have an outreach plan with clear, shared, objectives and a roadmap, have a mapping of the existing (e.g. initiatives, Partnerships), have a database of key actors. Thus to allow sharing of knowledge (e.g. Masterclass), coordinated collaboration (e.g. avoiding duplication), strategic discussions among Partnerships, and the setup of a community of practices.

In example situation 4 focusing on 'collaboration', the idea to have an outreach plan with clear objectives and roadmap was underlined. For doing this, one key action and one key tool were identified (in Table 8 below).

Key action or tool	Description
Mapping of the existing (e.g. initiatives)	The mapping allows to identify with whom the Partnership wants to collaborate: for reaching sustainability objectives and filling gaps (e.g. Topics), and for coordinated collaboration (e.g. avoiding duplication). In both case, there is a need to share knowledge. Exchange of information can be done in a small environment i.e. with other Partnerships dealing with sustainable food systems. An idea could be to create a space where Partnerships can have strategic discussions, and smaller environments could enhance efficient discussions. The main objective is to ensure that all the EU Partnerships are covering

	food systems and topics related. Another idea could be to make a Masterclass on various topics to teach other Partnerships key learnings on specific points, or do it as a knowledge exchange between Partnerships, exchange of experiences.
Database of actors active in each field related to food systems	The idea is to create a database per field/domain of activities (e.g. bioeconomy, fishery), initiatives/Partnerships that could be of interest for the Partnership SFS, giving some contact information and some other general information (e.g. actors involved, scale). Collaboration with other Partnerships would allow to create a 'community of practices' (e.g. good practices regarding the Modus Operandi) and to discuss about common needs (e.g. tools, administration incoherence or difficulties) that could be interesting to commonly voice to EU level (see ERA-Learn 'Platform').

6.1.3. How example situations illustrate success pillars

The table below (Table 9) summarizes how the 4 example situations illustrate the 9 success pillars:

↓ Success Pillars	Example situation 1: "Seeing the Light"	Example situation 2: "All Aboard"	Example situation 3: "Enlarging the Family"	Example situation 4: "Weaving Connections"
<p><i>Example situation Focus →</i></p> <p><i>Example situation key words →</i></p>	<p>Launch</p> <p><i>Launch, unfamiliar partners, engagement, internal communication, community building</i></p>	<p>Engagement</p> <p><i>Full participation, systems approach, SRIA update, stakeholder engagement both internal & external, flexibility in fund allocation, long-term trust building</i></p>	<p>Expansion</p> <p><i>Expansion, integration of new partners and funders, amendment to Grant Agreement, attracting international stakeholders, considerations of conflict of interest.</i></p>	<p>Collaboration</p> <p><i>Collaboration with other initiatives and Partnerships, establishing synergies through mapping and database creation, strategic discussions, and shared knowledge practices.</i></p>
<p>1. Ecosystem Network</p>	<p>Proactively develops offers and a target list to strategically expand the Partnership (e.g. geographical coverage). Understand the differences between other Partnerships.</p> <p><i>Regular meetings for proposals and funded projects: open info days (e.g. CBE), in-person info days at call launch (e.g. SBEP), annual events (for funded projects).</i></p>	<p>Employs fully participatory methods that engage all relevant partners and stakeholders and allow co-creation, enhancing the ecosystem's cohesion and functionality.</p> <p><i>Conduct coordination meetings of Partnerships from Cluster 6 and others (work together in writing the open calls to avoid overlaps).</i></p>	<p>Integrates new international funders and stakeholders, thereby broadening the global reach and diversity outside the EU.</p>	<p>Establishes a community of practices by mapping existing initiatives and Partnerships and sharing best practices across fields such as bioeconomy and fishery, fostering a collaborative ecosystem.</p> <p><i>Setup a database per field/domain of activities (e.g. bioeconomy, fishery), initiatives/Partnerships of interest with some contact information (e.g. actors, scale).</i></p>
<p>2. Dialogue & Consensus Building</p>	<p>Fosters an environment of trust and openness, using digital tools and event organization with set, regular occurrence for continuous engagement and consensus building within the consortium.</p> <p><i>Consortium meeting types: internal informal, networking meetings (e.g. FOODPathS monthly Café meetings), annual meetings.</i></p>	<p>Open consultations, organized workshops, and a mix of tools foster robust dialogue, consensus, and trust among diverse stakeholders, and with respect to the foundation of the SRIA as a guiding document.</p> <p><i>Setup a representative stakeholder consultative/overseeing committee/board?</i></p>	<p>Negotiates the integration of new partners, focusing on clear communication, agreement on roles, and consensus on governance standards to maintain trust and alignment.</p> <p>The integration of private funders is seen as a challenge due to potential Col for setting up calls, and regarding intellectual property rights and Partnership reputation in case of scandal with a company.</p>	<p>Establishes a community of practices to facilitate strategic discussions and consensus-building among different Partnerships, addressing common needs, administrative challenges, and avoid duplication.</p>

↓ Success Pillars	Example situation 1: "Seeing the Light"	Example situation 2: "All Aboard"	Example situation 3: "Enlarging the Family"	Example situation 4: "Weaving Connections"
3. Scientific Results & Impact	Have clear common objectives for orientation of calls.	Adaptability/resilience: ensures relevant and impactful research and innovation via a "window of flexibility" i.e. possibility to reallocate funds if "something bad" (?) happens. "Resilience fund" or "Adaptive research fund"?	*	*
4. Transfer to Policy	Set the framework for the programme/project and interaction with policy makers.	Stakeholder consultations and alignment of research initiatives with policy needs, to promote effective policy transfer.	Involves various governmental bodies, ministries and regions, ensuring that the expanded Partnership remains aligned with policy objectives and keeps its coherent decision-making process.	Strategic discussions and shared best practices among partnerships could influence policy by providing coordinated and well-informed insights into food system needs and solutions.
5. Transfer to Industry	Clarify the role of the private sector (private actors and associated networks) in the Partnership and possible ways to engage.	*	Makes knowledge easily accessible and understandable for SMEs & local business clusters.	*
6. Communication to Citizens	*	*	Discusses potential issues and solutions for integrating diverse funding sources, highlighting the importance of transparency and open communication with the broader public, to get the voices of civil society.	*
7. Training & Education	Utilizes informal meetings and events for skill development and knowledge sharing among partners.	*	*	Implements Masterclasses and knowledge exchanges to educate and train partners on specific topics, enhancing skill development and mutual learning across Partnerships.
8. Global Outreach	*	Utilizes strategic communications to inform and engage both internal and external stakeholders about ongoing initiatives and updates to the SRIA.	By including partners from outside the EU and discussing the inclusion of various regional actors, the scenario supports the Partnership's global outreach, ensuring that it remains relevant and effective internationally.	Setup an outreach plan with clear objectives and roadmap. By collaborating with international actors and sharing a database of initiatives, the Partnership can extend its global impact and fosters international cooperation.

↓ Success Pillars	Example situation 1: "Seeing the Light"	Example situation 2: "All Aboard"	Example situation 3: "Enlarging the Family"	Example situation 4: "Weaving Connections"
9. Sustainable Outcome & Shared Vision	Promotes a shared vision through active engagement, clear communication of functions and processes, and community building.	The participatory approach and systematic update of the SRIA support long-term sustainability and foster a shared vision for continuous improvement and adaptability within the Partnership's operational framework.	Focuses on creating a robust framework for governance and decision-making that accommodates new members while maintaining the integrity and sustainability of the Partnership. The scenario emphasizes the need for flexibility, transparency, and the inclusion of diverse voices to foster a shared vision that supports the transition to a SFS and robust governance.	The proactive outreach and strategic collaboration efforts ensure that all activities are aligned with the shared goals of creating a sustainable food system, demonstrating a clear commitment to long-term sustainability and effective partnership management.

* Not specifically addressed in this scenario.

6.2. Practical insights from the PTF4LS case study

In this and following sections (6.2, 6.3, 6.4), we present a selection of case studies that provide practical insights into the functioning of partnerships of diverse formats. These examples were selected not only based on the opportunities and resources available during the work on Task 2.3, but also for their potential to offer transferable lessons to the Partnerships, despite differing in scale, structure, and objectives. These cases represent successful practices, innovative governance models, and collaborative dynamics that can inform and inspire the Partnership.

The diversity of these case studies reflects the broader ecosystem of partnerships addressing food systems challenges, ranging from regional innovation clusters to transnational initiatives. Each example was chosen to highlight unique operational features, effective engagement strategies, or governance practices that contribute to sustainable outcomes. This illustrates the diversity of partnership approaches and underscores the value of learning from diverse experiences to define and adapt our own Modus Operandi. Through these insights, we aim to bridge the gap between theoretical recommendations and real-world applications.

This specific section presents the contributions and collaborative dynamics within the Platform Tecnológica Food for Life-Spain (PTF4LS), which was targeted as a model for effective public-private partnerships during a dedicated FOODPathS workshop in collaboration with WP4, at the EFFoST conference in November 2023. Organizations such as FIAB, CARTIF, UPV, IATA-CSIC, CDTI, and INGREDALIA each bring distinct strategic benefits to the network. The information was gathered directly from members of these organizations, during a dedicated workshop (see the 'Methods' section, this work is part of the task 2.3 process step 3). The results are presented in Table 10 below.

Question asked to responding organizations	Summary answer
<p>What is the added value of being part of this private-public network (examples of successes)? What are your organization's goals in participating in the PTF4LS?</p>	<p>Goals in participating:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FIAB: consolidate its leadership within the Spanish food sector by influencing national and European R&D directions, using the platform to foster collaboration and drive sector-wide policy and innovation initiatives. 2. CARTIF: enhance its technological influence and capacity for innovation, particularly in sustainable food systems, by engaging in collaborative R&D projects that align with global sustainability goals. 3. UPV: enhance its academic and research influence in the food service sector, aiming to integrate cutting-edge research and industry practices into its curriculum and outreach activities. 4. IATA-CSIC: align its scientific research with practical industry needs, aiming to translate its academic excellence into impactful technological innovations. 5. CDTI: optimize the alignment of governmental support with the innovative needs of the industry, facilitating effective funding and support mechanisms for R&D activities. 6. INGREDALIA: expand its collaborative opportunities, aiming to enhance its product offerings in the sustainability domain by leveraging advanced research and development insights from the network. <p>Participation in the PTF4LS network provides each member organization distinct strategic advantages.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FIAB enhances its influence on national and European R&D directions, effectively boosting innovation and policy development within the food sector. 2. CARTIF gains visibility and access to collaborative projects, which strengthens its position in technological innovation for sustainable food systems. 3. UPV leverages its leadership role to directly influence food service research and policy, enriching its educational and research initiatives.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. IATA-CSIC aligns its research with industry needs, enhancing the relevance and impact of its scientific endeavors. 5. CDTI utilizes its position to connect governmental funding and industry innovation, optimizing public investment in line with market demands. Each organization thus not only advances its own strategic objectives but also contributes significantly to the collective enhancement of Spain's R&D capabilities in the agri-food sector. 6. INGREDALIA uses its network participation to establish key partnerships and gain access to cutting-edge sustainability practices, significantly boosting its development of innovative, upcycled food ingredients and enhancing its visibility in the competitive agri-food market.
<p>How do you collaborate with the different actors? What is the positive contribution of private actors to the goals of this network?</p>	<p>Each organization within the PTF4LS network uses this position for effective collaboration and draws significant contributions from private actors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FIAB orchestrates industry-wide R&D efforts; 2. CARTIF tailors technological solutions with insights from private sector partners; 3. UPV enhances education through industry-relevant challenges; 4. IATA-CSIC integrates scientific research and needs and insights from the private sector to drive innovation; 5. CDTI connects Spanish companies to global R&D, with private companies enhancing project market alignment; 6. INGREDALIA works with larger companies to develop sustainable products, showcasing the vital role of SMEs in driving specific innovation within broader initiatives. <p>These collaborations demonstrate a robust model of public-private partnership that fuels innovation and addresses both commercial and scientific challenges in the agri-food sector.</p>
<p>Does the network include all relevant stakeholders?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FIAB presents the wide network that is PTF4LS, which yet may not cover all niche or emerging stakeholders. 2. CARTIF and UPV acknowledge broad collaboration (but do not specify 'completeness'). 3. IATA-CSIC sees room for more diverse and consumer-focused stakeholders. 4. CDTI emphasizes a comprehensive integration of R&D actors. 5. INGREDALIA feels well included and values the network's collaborative ecosystem, suggesting a generally positive perspective on stakeholder diversity. <p>These perspectives indicate both a robust and potentially expandable stakeholder network within PTF4LS.</p>
<p>As a member of the PTF4LS, how does your organization integrate the administrative and financial rules of the network? (for example contact person, resources invested...)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FIAB oversees governance structures, ensuring compliance across the network. 2. CARTIF actively engages in shaping and adhering to internal regulations and member assessments. 3. UPV and INGREDALIA participate in line with their organizational capacities and focus. Detailed mechanisms of their administrative integration are less specified. 4. IATA-CSIC manages its participation according to CSIC's public administration rules. 5. CDTI aligns its funding mechanisms with the network's administrative and financial rules. <p>We see diverse approaches to integrating complex administrative and financial rules within a collaborative R&D network like PTF4LS.</p>
<p>How does PTF4LS ensure a sense of belonging within the network? In your opinion, what specific</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FIAB, while not detailed, likely ensures belonging through its <u>wide representation</u> and involvement in the network. 2. CARTIF appreciates the <u>equal contribution structure</u>, and suggests <u>more collaborative events</u>.

<p>actions can be taken to enhance the sense of belonging?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. UPV and CDTI could further enhance belonging through better <u>visibility of impacts</u> and <u>interdisciplinary projects</u>. 4. IATA-CSIC values the <u>network's openness</u> and suggests more <u>diverse team collaborations</u>. 5. INGREDALIA appreciates the <u>equitable environment</u> and recommends more <u>leadership roles for SMEs</u> to deepen their sense of belonging. <p>The PTF4LS network supports a sense of belonging through structured, inclusive collaborations and a framework responsive to member needs. Each organization brings a unique perspective on fostering and enhancing belonging, reflecting the diverse nature of the network.</p>
<p>Based your experience in private-public cooperation, what strategies can be used to effectively involve the food industry in a future EU partnership on sustainable food systems?</p>	<p>The strategies to involve the food industry in the future EU partnership on sustainable food systems, as identified by the members of the PTF4LS, focus on <i>building strong relationships</i> and <i>leveraging common goals</i>.</p> <p>IATA-CSIC highlights the importance of <i>creating trust</i> and <i>pursuing mutual interests</i> to foster collaboration.</p> <p>Although other organizations like FIAB, CARTIF, CDTI, UPV, and INGREDALIA did not provide specific strategies or suggestions, the general involvement of these organizations in a variety of R&D and funding activities suggests a broader approach of <i>integrating industry needs with collaborative research and development efforts within the EU framework</i>.</p> <p>Further details on strategies from these organizations would require additional specific information or direct consultation.</p>

These results outline how these organizations not only achieve their individual goals but also collectively enhance Spain's R&D capabilities in the agri-food sector through the PTF4LS platform. Additionally, the data explore mechanisms of collaboration among diverse actors, stakeholder inclusivity, adherence to network-wide administrative and financial rules, and methods to foster a sense of belonging and equitable participation. We found that such a structured approach not only augments the capacities of individual organizations but also amplifies the network's overall coherence and impact.

6.3. Practical insights from three INRAE in-depth case studies

After gathering 72 diverse food system cases across Europe, in-depth case studies were conducted on three unique partnerships: Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM) in France, Foodwest in Finland, and BIOEAST spanning Central-Eastern European countries. Each partnership was analyzed through ten interviews per case, conducted in 2023, with various stakeholders to explore governance models, involved actors, co-created value, and visions for sustainability. These partnerships, representing a range of geographical scales and organizational types, provide insights into the dynamics and effectiveness of different collaborative approaches within the food system. The findings from these interviews are detailed in Table 11 that highlights the modus operandi elements identified during the study, helping to better understand the operational intricacies and strategic ambitions of these partnerships.

Practical feature category of modus operandi	Summary elements from case studies	Main takeaways
Dissemination & communication	A variety of tools are used within the Modus Operandi, with a unique mix selected for each case, even though some tools may recur across different initiatives. Given the wide range of options, each initiative chooses its mix according to its specific context and partnership needs. The most commonly used tools include workshops and events, internal results reports, official websites to showcase outcomes (both in the national language and in English), and agreements that assign responsibilities to universities.	The choice of communication channels should include online platforms for daily operations, as well as occasional on-site events to strengthen partnership cohesion. Formal and informal approaches should be clearly distinguished, with tools adapted to each situation (i.e., what is valuable to share broadly), while keeping transparency as a key requirement.
Engagement & collaboration	Initiatives may rely on informal processes that do not involve intermediaries—such as web platforms that allow partners to connect directly or word of mouth to introduce new partners. Going further, each case often seeks to gain insights from partners' experiences, which can help address various needs in line with the partnership's objectives. In the case of BIOEAST, it is noteworthy that a handbook was developed to support all partners in collaborating more effectively. Strategies are thus diverse: BIOEAST tries to share and capitalize knowledge of its partners while Foodwest and Pôle Mer Méditerranée are more focus on creating new knowledge and know-how.	Offer a wide range of channels when seeking new partners. At the same time, clarifying the partnership's objectives—specifically where collaboration is needed and which partners have relevant experience—can be very useful. The Modus Operandi should include tools to support partners who may lack experience in this area. These tools can be formal (such as handbooks, presentations, etc.) or informal (such as one-on-one exchanges), depending on the situation—for example, if the context is specific to a particular project setting
Strategic & planning	All the partnerships studied involve collaboration between the board and partner representatives. The board's level of authority varies depending on the case: in some instances, it has final decision-making power on general strategy, while in others, it shares this power partially. Partners are either consulted or represented on the board through elected representatives (e.g., PMM).	Follow a formal process (such as elections) with rules agreed upon by all partners at the outset, allowing for modifications over time if necessary, to ensure fairness and stability.

Review & feedback	informal one-on-one discussions with coordinators, board members, or intermediaries are used across all cases. The board then decides if any actions or decisions are needed. Only PMM follows a highly formal review process, due to their "competitive pole" label, which must be renewed every five years.	Combine informal feedback, to gather direct impressions, with formal feedback methods, such as anonymous questionnaires that allow everyone to share their views on an equal footing.
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6.4. Good practices in projects managed by INRAE Transfert

The INRAE Transfert's European Department has managed over 100 European projects since 2004. A workshop using the 'Appreciative Interviews' technique to identify key project management practices based on this collective experience was conducted in October 2024. The 28 participants (90% of the Department) shared and discussed successful experiences, using feedback to formalize effective management strategies.

The results show critical success factors across **five main categories**, essential for effective project management according to INRAE Transfert. They are presented in Table 12. These include coordination and management team functioning, where key practices such as frequent communication, regular meetings, and a clear definition of roles between the coordinator and project manager are emphasized. Moreover, the relationship between the coordination team and the consortium is crucial, with strategies like sharing responsibilities and setting clear management processes to improve collaboration and internal communication. The session also underscored the importance of engaging project events, monitoring and reporting mechanisms, and strategic exploitation of project results to foster innovation and long-term vision. These comprehensive strategies are designed to enhance project outcomes through structured management and responsive interactions among all project participants.

Category:
Coordination/management team functioning (composed in our case of INRAE coordinator and IT project manager)
<p>Conditions for success:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish frequent/regular communication between the coordinator and the project manager. - Fix regular meetings between the coordinator and the project manager (one per week, or one every two weeks, frequency can be higher depending on the period). - Organize regular feedbacks between the coordinator and the project manager on their functioning in order to improve interactions. - Setup a frame clarifying the role and missions of the coordinator and the project manager (can be redefined as the project activities progress). - The coordinator need to dedicate enough time to the coordination, fulfill his/her duties, and organize his/her time to effectively focus on urgent and important actions. - Have internal (institutional) support on coordinator side and project manager side. Having two or three coordinators, if the role/missions are clear, can be beneficial. - Have a precise schedule of coordination/management actions and who should take care of what. Possibility to setup a 'to do list' for the coordinator using digital tools (e.g. Trello). - The project manager shall be involved as early as possible in order to be well integrated in the project. - The human qualities of the coordinator to successfully lead the consortium are crucial. The project manager needs to adapt to the coordinator personality. A privileged and trusting relationship is important between the coordinator and the project manager (ideally they should be present on the same working place). - The coordinator needs to be efficient (to be replaced in case of deficient). He/she must be present with a good vision of the project and its surrounding. - The project manager needs to be organized, proactive, adaptable. - The coordination/management team needs to quickly adapt to unexpected situations e.g. an uncooperative partner.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The coordination/management team shall activate the governing bodies when needed and depending on the situation.
<p>Relationship between the coordination team and the consortium, and among the consortium</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share the responsibilities so that the coordinator does not have the responsibility of everything, allows for better appropriation of the project outputs/tasks. Implementation of a review system by the consortium i.e. relieve the coordinator of delegable tasks (e.g. to review deliverables). - Carry out an early diagnosis (first weeks of project launch/support) of interactions with key people (WP leaders, partners) and adjust approaches accordingly to improve the collaboration. Adapt the support method and tools according to the interlocutor. - Define clear management processes to be followed by the coordinator and the consortium. Setup efficient management tools for the coordination team but also for the consortium. - Favor the communication among partners, e.g. organize a chart with photographs of project partners for the visibility (if public), and to know 'who is who' (this can be done in an original way using a whiteboard like Klaxoon); setup a contact list with links to LinkedIn accounts of partners. - The coordination team shall well know the consortium partners and adapt its communication to their needs. The internal communication is crucial. The coordination team shall create a good atmosphere to favor good relations between partners.
<p>Project events</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During the project annual meetings, plan some free time (several hours) for free exchanges among participants and to allow them to self-organize discussions/meetings at smaller scales. - Before the project annual meetings, plan some preparatory meetings (by videoconference) to fix some issues in order to deal with the most important ones during the annual meetings. - Before the project annual meetings, organize some webinars to present the state of progress of the WPs in order to favor exchanges and collaborative work on specific topics during the annual meetings. - Prior to the meetings, provide template of presentations to WP leaders with a specific frame to follow, e.g. work progress, difficulties, deliverable in progress, and risk. The WP leader can also use them during the WP leaders meetings (executive committee = body responsible for project implementation and monitoring). - Organize innovative activities favoring the exchanges among participants i.e. world market (stand, poster) to present the work performed during the previous year (can be done per WP); interactive workshop on the project results/impact (for the long term vision); fish bowl to exchange on what was learnt during the meeting and the define together the next steps. - Organize some 'informal' moments, e.g. ice breakers (good for group cohesion). - Prior to the meetings, provide templates of minutes to follow. At the end of each project events, make minutes to track important discussions with a table summary of actions planned.
<p>Project monitoring and reporting</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the reporting to the EC, setup a simple process and share files using online tools (e.g. Nextcloud, SharePoint) allowing to access the most up to date version. - Establish a good relationship between the coordination team and the project funder. And find solutions together to face changes in the workplan. - Follow the deliverables and data derived from them in order to facilitate the project monitoring.
<p>Project results exploitation and impact</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize exchanges to think about the future. Important to have a 'vision', notably a long-term vision. - Have an active Innovation Management Group (composed of actors agreeing to go beyond science) from the project start in order to follow the exploitable results. Nominate a facilitator to bring this group to life and animate it. Associate the WP leaders (executive committee = body responsible for project implementation and monitoring). - The 'proximity' between researchers and field actors allows for the co-creation of solutions to better adapt to field actor needs. - The relationship of trust between public and private actors (relationship even before the start of the project) facilitates their collaboration.

7. Annex 3: Full list of ideas from individual post-its during phase 1 of the workshop “Dreamt Future”

1. Ecosystem network

- The Partnership has developed a **strong ecosystem of actors across the food chain** where there is high trust and effective collaboration.
- The Partnership has successfully drawn the retail sector into the R&I ecosystem.
- Good use & growth of (already) existing **knowledge platforms**.
- A **strong research community** that drives systems-oriented changes.
- **Strong & functional ties with other ‘partnerships’**.
- Co-creation and exchange with other Partnerships (e.g Agroecology).
- A **multi-actor network**. In the ideal Partnership, ‘I’ have contacts to all kind of different actors.
- **Geographical balance**.

2. Dialogue & consensus building

- The Partnership is the place where **stakeholders discourse about their divergent opinions and succeed in finding a compromise**, rather than to stop/delay the adoption of actions/regulation.
- The Partnership acts as a **neutral entity enhancing collaboration** using adapting tools in a continuous improvement process.
- Food system actors **seeking knowledge and tools** to ensure their operations are as sustainable as possible (from farmers to policy makers).
- **Knowledge sharing**: engage with communities (e.g. local), organise workshops/ events/ seminars, policy makers have evidence-based recommendations.
- **Stakeholder engagement**: governments shapes regional and national agenda, with support of producers/farmers, consumers.

3. Scientific results & impact (link with 4 and 5)

- Well performing projects generating **innovative results**.
- 50 R&I projects funded each year and generating **high quality R&I with impact**.
- Fund and manage a wide range of **excellent and innovative projects at different TRLs**.
- A scientist icon, a Nobel prize for a result that was generated thanks to funding received of the Partnership.
- **Impactful research** changed the diets of citizens to sustainable option.
- Sound knowledge base about **food system transformation (observatory)**.
- Food system observatory for the EU that produces state of the art knowledge on our food systems to facilitate **agile and data driven transitions**.
- **Research outputs are well spread** inside and outside Partnership in an adaptative language.
- Good projects > impactful results > shape policy > informs society.

4. Science to policy (link with 3)

- Successfully set up a science to policy interface to ensure that the knowledge produced in the WPs and calls is implemented in the **transition of food systems**.
- Policy makers receive basis for their work.
- The Partnership has become the ‘go-to’ group for policy **input for EC and Member States (MS)**.

5. Co-creation with industry (link with 3)

- **Uptake** of research results from food operators.
- Industries **improve process and reduce by products/waste, energy consumption, water**.

6. Consultation and communication to citizens (link to 7)

- The majority of the EU citizens knows about the Partnership and the **benefits it had on their lives**.
- Researchers have clearly and **successfully communicated to citizens** what they have done thanks to the Partnership.
- **Consultations to improve/update the SRIA** are largely participated by citizens and CSO (Civil Society Organisations).
- **Transfer of knowledge** to EU citizens in their own language (videos, comics...).
- **Common language and clear definitions**.
- Citizens are **relevant impactful end-users** of projects.
- **Everybody knows the Partnership**. The Partnership succeed/success in communicating results to citizens and experts.

7. Training & education (link to 6)

- **Schools** participate to living labs (transfer of knowledge).

8. Global outreach (link with 4, 5, 6)

- **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of project results** into knowledge + innovation transfer.
- Communication → Journalism + Media. Explain what it is (awareness, funders).

9. Sustainable outcome & shared vision

- **Strategic action plan running**.
- **Open & transparent & trustful** operational process in place.
- **Strong interpartners collaboration** to cover the full food system.
- **Good synergy** with other existing networks, Partnerships, projects.
- **Highly attractive** to join or connect to (being part of).
- **Clear signs of a transition to Sustainable Food System (SFS)**. “A new hope created” that we can reach SFS.
- Tipping point to transition to a SFS is reached, thanks also to the Partnership.
- Both the EC and MS want to continue the Partnership for another 7 years.
- Successfully leveraged **more funds than MS/AC** (Associated Countries) than was specified in GA.
- Self-sufficient.
- **Image/legacy**: well respected, active, good reputation, funded, well known, profile.
- **Time and resources** for participation conducting to inclusion, coaching programme.
- Strongly embedded in each MS & globally actively involved actors from all stakeholder groups.
- **Show-case 100+ examples** (creating a snow ball effect).

8. Annex 4: Facilitator guide for the Modus Operandi workshop on Ideal Partnership

Some terms initially present in this guide have been changed when working on the deliverable D2.5 i.e. 'scenario' had been replaced by 'example situations'.

Agenda

Workshop facilitator version

Most of the facilitator's action will be in both activities of Step 2 highlighted in pink:

#	Item	Indicative time	Supporting material
0.	Introduction (Plenary, 10 minutes)	08:30 - 08:40	PowerPoint
1.	Step 1: Dreamt ideal partnership (Plenary, 20 minutes)	08:40 - 09:00	
	- Presentation (5')		PowerPoint
	- Brainstorming (5')		'Solo time' with post-its
	- Sharing and pooling (10')		Flipchart sheets
2.	Step 2: Ideal scenarios illustrating the partnership processes (Tables, 55 minutes)	09:00 - 09:55	
	- Presentation (5')		PowerPoint
	- Activity 2.1: Scriptwriting (40')		Tables, Post-its and pens, flipchart sheet, this guide
	- Activity 2.2: Testing and updating (10')		
3.	Step 3: Story-telling and assessment (Plenary feedback) (Plenary, 30 minutes)	09:55 - 10:25	Stage
	- Opening scene (session facilitator, 30")		(PowerPoint?)
	- Scenario (story-teller, 2')		Flipchart sheet with scenario
	- Assessment (All, 3')		Vote post-its on flipchart
	- Loop x 4-5 tables/scenarios		
4.	Conclusions and perspectives (Plenary, 5 minutes)	10:25 - 10:30	PowerPoint

Step 0: introduction (10')

Context, definition of modus operandi, overall presentation of activity.

Present:

- The process for conducting task 2.3
 - How today's workshop fits in this process

- The rationale behind the proposed workshop activity (dream features / scriptwriting) and the link to the modus operandi
- The next steps: identify the prerequisites of those scenarios focusing on the modus operandi

Step 1: Dreamt ideal partnership (Plenary, 20')

[Pitch] May 12, 2032. The partnership for sustainable food systems has now been running for the better part of its initially foreseen duration (8+ years), and by all accounts it has become the ideal partnership everyone had dreamt of. You are a member of the ideal partnership. Describe how it performs, what its successes/features are.

Sequence

1. Presentation of activity (PPT slide): question, support, sequence
2. Brainstorming and post-it generation (each participant on their own; 1 post-it for each feature of the partnership)
3. Sharing and pooling: putting together all post-its (plenary on flipchart)
4. Categorizing ideas. Examples of categories:
 - a. *Outcomes*: results, internal features
 - b. *Practical features*: formal framework, secretariat, internal communication, indicators/monitoring
5. Keep the results displayed for the rest of the workshop (inspiration for Step 2)

Activity 1.1: Brainstorming (5')

Instructions:

“May 12, 2032. The partnership for sustainable food systems has now been running for the majority of its initially foreseen life cycle (8+ years) and by all accounts, it has become the ideal partnership everyone had dreamt of. You are a member of the ideal partnership. **Describe how it performs, what its successes/features are.**”

Who is “you”? throughout the workshop please perform the activities as:

- Yourself (with your own experience e.g. in past projects/networks/partnerships)
- Your organization
- The stakeholder group you represent

Helping questions:

- In your opinion, what should the ideal partnership achieve on a daily to yearly basis?
- Who contacts and seeks the services of the partnership? To cover what kinds of needs?

Examples:

“The ideal partnership...

- ... is known by all relevant actors in the field.”
- ... is an integral part of the EC’s policy design process.”
- ... allows for quick and adaptive decision making.”

“As a member of the ideal partnership...

- ... I know very well all the other members.”
- ... I feel part of a strong and mutually beneficial community.”

Activity 1.2: Sharing and pooling (10')

- The session facilitator(s) ask(s) for one idea (or all of them) to one participant; displays the post-it(s) on the flipchart
- The session facilitator(s) select(s) one post-it and asks if other participants had the same or connected ones; goes down the list of post-its; participants share their ideas
- Inclusion of new ideas when one category appears exhausted
- Categories of ideal features emerge as ideas as shared and pooled (e.g. internal vs. external, benefits for partners vs. EU, external stakeholders...)

Step 2: Ideal scenarios illustrating the partnership processes (55')

[Pitch] We still are in the dreamt partnership, a few years prior i.e. right in the middle of its life cycle. The partnership is presented with one practical situation or event. Narrate how the ideal partnership receives and handles this event step by step.

Definitions (from the movie universe)

Opening scene = starting point of the ideal scenario. Context, environmental features and other details illustrating the imaginary but realistic situation which the partnership needs to deal with.

Scenario = complete story written collectively by the table.

Actor / Role = each participant at the table, and also each of the complementary roles in the partnership.

Author / Authors = participant(s) to the table during the initial round (Activity 1), who contribute(s) to designing the scenario (before it is updated).

Scriptwriter = participant who takes notes at the table. Depositary of the collectively written scenario.

Story-telling = plenary feedback from the table to all workshop participants.

Sequence

1. Presentation of activity (PPT slide): context, support, sequence
2. **Group formation** from prearranged group list
3. **Actors get into the scene and into their role** (reading, understanding, entering in my role)
4. **Writing the scenario:**
 - a. Discussion: imagining the step-by-step unfolding
 - b. Scriptwriting
5. **Testing and updating the scenario:**
 - a. Half participants (2-3) from each table go to another table
 - b. Authors run the script by the new actor(s)
 - c. Feedback and update process

The 5 scenarios

Five different scenarios are discussed in the workshop, one at each table. The scenarios are complementary all together. Each scenario illustrates one working method of the partnership through an example or practical situation of the partnership's activities. Each scenario starts with an "opening scene" and question defined before the workshop starts, and is then written in the context of this opening scene. Depending on the selected scenarios, there could be variants (e.g. different types of partners, different geographical areas...) which the table could address to enrich and consolidate the process designed in the scenario.

Support and group composition

- **Room setting:** group or table
 - 4-5 tables
 - 4-6 participants per table
- Distribution of **workshop functions** at the table:
 - 1 facilitator participant: *guides the table with the help of the workshop guide*
 - 1 scriptwriter (note-taker) participant: *takes notes in a visual manner on a flipchart sheet with markers, as visual support of the plenary feedback step.*
 - 2-4 more participants
- Distribution of **roles** in the scenario at the table:
 - The background and role of participants should be complementary and cover most roles found in the partnership. The role may be defined based on the components or WP of the partnership, or stakeholder groups.
 - Roles: coordination, funder, communicator...
 - Stakeholder groups: policy makers, academic, scientists, private sector...

Introduction: Getting into the scene and into the roles (5')

- The table facilitator reads the **opening scene** out loud for the table.
- The facilitator distributes **actor cards** at each table, each with the role written on it. Actors place their card in front of them at the table. Cards are color coded per type of actor (one of the same role/color at each table).
- Roundtable: each participant reads their **role** in the ideal partnership (e.g. 'funder'), may complete with how it connects with their present role in real life.

Activity 2.1: Scriptwriting: step-by-step unfolding of the scenario (40')

Instructions:

"We still are in the dreamt partnership, a few years prior i.e. right in the middle of its life cycle. The partnership is presented with one practical situation or event. **Narrate how the ideal partnership receives and handles this event step by step.**"

- Either spontaneous first thoughts by participants and ensuing discussion, *and/or* the table facilitator initiates a roundtable: each participant reminds their role in the ideal partnership and states one action they would take in this capacity in the partnership.
 - "As funder/communicator/scientist I would do... I would need information X or Y..."
- The scriptwriter takes notes and produces the scenario i.e. a step-by-step course of actions taken by the Ideal Partnership to deal with the situation.
- Actors react to a first version of the scenario and update / enrich / go more in-depth in the response of the partnership to the situation.

Helping questions:

- Remind your role in the partnership, and in this capacity share one idea how you would react to this situation.
- In your own experience or in your organization's history, how did you react to one (or more) similar situation(s)?
- *Scriptwriter reads first version of scenario.*
 - Which steps are missing?
 - Are all the information need for each step available, or should we seek information/advice/make decisions in the steps before?
 - Can you go more in-depth in the level of detail of each step?

- What are the data or documents generated at each step (e.g. emails, videoconference meeting, quotations, contracts...)? Who are they shared with / at which moment / how are they stored or disposed of afterwards?

Activity 2.2: Testing and updating the scenario (10')

- Half of actors (2-3) from each table go to another table (the facilitator and scriptwriter stay).
- The scriptwriter or another author tells the scenario
- Discussion: the new actor(s) ask(s) questions, share(s) their perspective; back-and-forth discussion with the script authors (all remaining participants at the table).
 - *Helping questions: in your role in the partnership, how would you react in this situation? How would you expect the ideal partnership to react? (Also see the helping questions of Activity 2.1)*
- The scriptwriter updates the scenario as needed to integrate the new feedback

Step 3: Story-telling and assessment (30')

[Pitch/instructions] We are in 2028 and it is project review time after the second reporting period of the Ideal Partnership. You are a reviewer tasked by the EC REA to assess the technical report submitted by the partnership's consortium.

The REA tries out a new process for reviewers with the following instruction: "please carefully assess the live report of activities, then provide feedback directly on the visual support with 3 post-its".

Sequence

1. One story-teller from each table comes to the stage: *table facilitator, scriptwriter, or another author who stayed at the table during the whole of Step 2*
2. 30": The session facilitator tells the opening scene of the first table (and makes the transition between each table/scenario)
3. 2': The story-teller tells the rest of the scenario i.e. how it unfolds from the opening scene
4. 3': Participants give their feedback directly on the visual support with 3 post-its: 'upvote' (green; *critical step to keep*), 'warning' (red; *step to clarify or adapt*), and one 'suggested improvement' (yellow; *write the suggestion on the post-it*).

Questions to solve:

- Order of tables? (Links from one scenario to the next?)
- Better 4 or 6 participants per table?
 - If 25 participants = 5 tables of 5
 - If 20-24 participants = 5 tables of 4-5, or 4 tables of 5-6
 - If 4-5 scenarios, which scenario is dropped?

